

The Relevance of Implementing CRM Systems in a Pharmaceutical Company

Alimzhanova L.M.

Candidate of Technical Sciences,
Associate Professor of the Department
"Information Systems" of the International University of
Information Technologies, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Tumaruly Aidar

Master degree student
"7M06104 IT Project Management",
JSC International University of Information Technologies,
Almaty, Kazakhstan,

Abstract:- This article highlights the significance of a CRM system as a customer-oriented business idea, the necessity of its implementation to standardize staff interactions with clients, and the automation of these interactions' necessary processes. Both the organization as a whole and each of its specific business processes—the efficiency of which is directly dependent upon good customer communication—are displayed together with the functional capabilities of CRM systems. Based on CRM's beneficial effects on an organization's core operations in the contemporary market, a list of options for complete control over client interactions—whose loyalty determines any company's success—is offered.

Keywords:- CRM System, Customer, Business, Deployment, Administration, Coordination, And Functionality.

I. INTRODUCTION

The modern market offers us unlimited opportunities to choose goods or services. Messages about promotions and discounts are regularly sent to the mailbox, informational calls with offers to use the services of a particular company are received on the phone, catch-up advertising with an offer to buy goods regularly appears on the Internet. The problem is that all goods and services are now generally about the same. It is quite difficult to find significant differences, often they do not bother the client at all.

The competitive struggle in such conditions becomes especially acute. Attraction new customers cost money, but after they are attracted, they also need to be retained. You need to please the client and build a successful and long-term relationship with him, or make sure that he at least does not remain dissatisfied after contacting the company or making a purchase. One dissatisfied customer can deprive the company of another dozen potential customers. How to build a good relationship with a client? How to keep him and not let him go to competitors? How to arrange it for a repeat purchase?

The implementation of a CRM system will help solve these issues. I'll get better right away, by itself the implementation itself will not become a magic wand, at the

wave of which customers will immediately become satisfied and loyal to your company as a whole or to the product in particular. CRM is a tool that you need to master. If we talk about modern CRM, then this is a set of tools that helps businesses build relationships with customers. [1]

CRM (customer relationship management) is, literally, an abbreviation that stands for customer relationship management. In a direct sense, this is software that allows you to collect, store and work with customer information, keep records of communications, plan cases, prepare documents and analyze customer data.

CRM is also a business concept aimed at a good knowledge of your client, establishing successful relationships with the client and improving the quality of customer service, which should eventually lead to an increase in the company's competitive advantages, increase profits and optimize the company's activities as a whole. [2]

In addition to the functionality of collecting, storing and processing information, modern CRM systems allow you to automate routine processes in the company. For example, automatically generate documents based on data from CRM (commercial offers, contracts, invoices, acts), schedule calls and meetings, send e-mail and SMS messages. In addition to these functions, the CRM system allows you to standardize the work of employees with clients and makes it transparent for the manager. Standardization of work involves the creation of work regulations in CRM. Filling in all the necessary information about the client according to the same rules. Telephone communication with the client from corporate numbers, sending letters from corporate mail and a single type of documents.

In the absence of a CRM system, each employee maintains their customer base as follows as he wants. It can be stored as numbers in a phone, in a notebook, or in tables. Things are planned in the diary. Such methods of maintaining a customer base can be effective only if the employee himself is effective. If he really enters it into his database after the client's request, he will not forget to send him an offer and call him back. [3]

The implementation and use of a CRM system implies the standardization of work with incoming requests for each employee. For example, let's analyze working with a client in the CRM of a sales manager:

➤ *Processing an incoming request.*

In modern CRM systems, any client's request, whether it is an incoming call, a new e-mail, a message on social networks, filling out a feedback form on the company's website, is automatically registered in the system and requires processing. The sales department employee must respond to the request and process it. Identify the client's need, enter the information into the database and start preparing a proposal that satisfies the client's request.

➤ *Registration of the request in the database.*

Connecting all communication channels to CRM makes it possible to register all customer requests and work with them. It is impossible to forget about registered appeals, the system constantly shows them as unprocessed and requires the participation of an employee. By default, the systems are able to record the following data about the client:

- When a phone call is made, the phone number from which the call was made is registered in the system.
- When an incoming message is sent from a new mailbox, its address is registered in the system.
- When filling out the feedback form, the data that the client left about himself is recorded in the system.
- When contacting from social networks, the name of the social network from which the request was received and the user's name are registered in the system.

The task of the employee at this stage is to identify the needs of the client and enter information about him into his database. For example, if we sell real estate agencies, the sales department employee must find out exactly what the client is looking for, whether he is going to buy real estate or sell it. What kind of real estate is this? House, apartment or parking space? The employee must find out this data and enter it into his database. After it is filled in the client's card, his contact details, his requests and additional information, the sales staff begins to prepare an offer for the client.

➤ *Offer.*

At this stage, the employee must prepare an offer, send it to the client and present it. Here, the CRM system will automatically generate an offer based on the goods and services that are included in the system. The generated offer can be sent to the client directly from the system or printed out and sent by mail.

➤ *Preparation of documents for the transaction.*

If all the previous stages were successful and the client was satisfied with the commercial offer it's time to sign the contract. If the company is missing CRM system the manager asks the client to send a card with the details of the company and begins to prepare the contract. He transfers the data from

the card to the contract, coordinates and signs it with the manager and sends it to the client. Manual filling out, approval and signing of the contract is routine work and takes a lot of time. Modern CRM systems allow you to automatically form contracts based on the data that has been entered into the system. Business processes of approval documents allow you to coordinate and send documents for processing by clicking one button. The employee has automatically formed a contract and, if it needs to be agreed with the manager, he starts the business process of approving documents. The manager receives a notification that his participation in the approval of the document is required. If the document meets all the requirements, the responsible person clicks the approve button, and the employee who started the process receives a notification about it, or, if the document requires revision, the person responsible for approval rejects the document and sends it for revision, which is also notified to the employee who started the process.

➤ *Completion of the transaction.*

After the contract has been signed, after the transaction has been completed, it must be closed with documents. And here the CRM system provides us with the opportunity to automatically generate the documents necessary for closing the transaction based on the data from the client's card. As a result, we get a loyal client whose application was processed quickly and efficiently, and his need was met. [4]

Modern CRM systems should have approximately the following functionality for successful work with clients:

- Informative directories are just the section in which information about the client is stored (full name, company name, position, phone number, e-mail) Properly configured directories will allow you to create a portrait of the client, form lists of clients according to the specified parameters, form documents based on this data and build a marketing strategy of the company based on customer portraits.
- Integration with IP telephony - registration of incoming and outgoing calls is mandatory if you do not want to miss a single client. Properly configured telephony automatically distributes calls among employees according to the specified settings. Records conversations with clients, if necessary. The call can be made both from the system itself, from the client's card, and from the telephone, and the information about the call will still pass through the system and register the call in it. The customized voice menu allows the new client to choose which department of the company he needs to contact.
- Integration with e-mail – registration of incoming emails directly in the client's card, will reduce the time needed to search for emails. All emails are attached directly to customer relationship stories, send emails in some systems too it is possible directly from the client card, avoiding switching between the system and the mailbox.
- Business processes – this function will allow you to transfer existing processes in the company to CRM. For example,

applications for vacation or cash withdrawal, approval of documents.

- Reports – I allow you to generate analytical reports on transactions, clients, products and managers' performance.

In general, the introduction of CRM in the conditions of the modern market will allow you to realize the following opportunities:

- take control of all channels of communication with customers;
- increase the speed and quality of processing incoming applications and, as a result, increase sales growth;
- create a customer base customized for a specific type of business;
- to establish control and transparency of transactions by employees;
- automate the document flow in the company, eliminate errors in the formation of documents;
- create a unified communication space for employees.
- automate business processes in the company;
- analyze the quality of transactions using the sales funnel tool, see at what stages transactions fail, work on weaknesses and improve the strong;
- analyze employee performance. [4]

Of the minuses:

- cost, the implementation of a CRM system requires money;
- the need to rebuild the scheme of the company's work.

II. CONCLUSION

To implement a CRM system or not to implement it, of course, each company should independently, having weighed all the pros and cons. The market of CRM systems is now actively developing and more and more companies are using both the CRM concept and CRM systems in doing business, and companies that postpone implementation risk being in the ranks of "catching up".

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